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Energy-Efficient Hull-Propeller-Engine Matching Optimization via Cooperative Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract. Optimizing the hull-propeller-engine matching is crucial for improving fuel efficiency and reducing emissions. Traditional methods often rely on simplified models that fail to account for the complex, dynamic interactions between the components. This paper proposes a novel approach that leverages Cooperative Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning (CMARL) to address the hull-propeller-engine matching problem. In our framework, a multi-agent system learns to optimize its parameters while cooperating to achieve the best overall performance. The system’s goal is to minimize fuel consumption while maintaining the design speed. To avoid the computational complexity of CFD simulations, we utilize surrogate models to estimate ship resistance. The system is responsible for selecting the main ship dimensions to calculate resistance from the surrogate model, determining the most suitable propeller characteristics using B-series propeller design charts, and selecting the optimal engine from a database. The learning process is driven by Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), a state-of-the-art reinforcement learning algorithm. This allows the system to handle the high dimensionality of the problem and continuous-discrete hybrid spaces. Our results demonstrate that the trained system reduces fuel consumption by 5% within a highly constrained design space. Furthermore, the system can be adapted to different design speeds without retraining. This approach offers significant advantages over traditional methods by providing a scalable and flexible way to obtain an optimal hull-propeller-engine matching, enhancing fuel efficiency.

Key words: Hull-propeller-engine Matching, Fuel Consumption, Reinforcement Learning, Cooperative Learning, Proximal Policy Optimization

1. Introduction

Hull-propeller-engine matching at the conceptual design stage is a challenging task, demanding both a deep understanding of the system’s underlying physics and substantial design experience. Because this problem is a high-dimensional problem, involving numerous variables and constraints—such as the ship’s length, breadth, propeller diameter, propeller pitch, and engine power—an optimal solution is difficult to obtain. In the traditional approach, designers typically employ the design spiral [1] to find a feasible solution. They first determine the ship’s geometry to minimize resistance, then select the engine based on estimated power requirements, and subsequently size the propeller according to resistance and engine power, repeating this process iteratively. However, this approach is highly sensitive to the initial value, is labor-intensive and fails to explore the entire design space, making it prone to converging easily to suboptimal solutions.

Optimization algorithms have been applied to address this problem. Xu [2] employed a genetic algorithm to develop a system for hull-propeller-engine matching. However, Xu’s optimization objective was propeller efficiency, rather than fuel consumption, which is the primary concern for shipowners. Actually, “the optimal matching might be due to neither the most efficient propeller

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nor the most efficient engine, but instead due to the best combination itself” [3]. Furthermore, facing the need to reduce the emission of carbon dioxide, fuel consumption has become the dominant optimization objective in this problem. Ren et al. [4] used the Energy Efficient Design Index (EEDI) as the objective function but only analyzed its influence on ship speed, propeller diameter, and effective power without identifying a feasible integrated solution. Marques et al. [5] applied a differential evolution algorithm to minimize fuel consumption and proposed a systematic framework for matching a Wageningen B-screw series propeller—designed via optimization—with an engine selected from a database of available options. Despite these advances, optimization algorithms still face challenges in efficiently handling such high-dimensional problems. As a result, most approaches either reduce the problem’s dimensionality or adopt a granular workflow to decompose it into smaller sub-problems.

Recently, Design Automation and Intelligence have emerged as a rapidly growing field that integrates artificial intelligence with Model-Based Design. Reinforcement Learning (RL) has been successfully applied to engineering problems characterized by high-dimensional action-state spaces and numerous constraints. Hayashi and Ohsaki [6] combined RL with metaheuristics to design plane frames and found that the trained agent was robust to variations in the initial solution, number of stories and number of spans. Xu et al. [7] employed multi-agent RL to develop a novel framework for home energy management demonstrating “excellent decision-making capability in the absence of initial environment information.” Furthermore, Dworschak [8] highlighted the potential of RL in advancing Design Automation.

However, not all RL algorithms are suitable for this problem, as both the state and action spaces are high-dimensional and constitutes a hybrid of discrete and continuous components. Early RL methods, such as Q-learning [9] and actor-critic architectures [10], are unable to effectively handle high-dimensional or continuous spaces and often fail even on moderately complex tasks. Deep Q-Networks [11] addressed this limitation by introducing deep neural networks to approximate the non-linear Q-value function, extending RL to more complex problems. As a result, RL with Deep Neural Network (DNN) has become a widely used framework. However, training deep RL algorithms is time-consuming and unstable. To improve training stability and efficiency, algorithms such as Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [12] and Soft Actor-Critic (SAO) [13] have been proposed. These methods have been successfully applied to high-dimensional problems, such as the 21-dimensional Humanoid [13]. Nevertheless, SAC is primarily designed for continuous action spaces and is less suitable for problems involving significant discrete decision variables. Given the hybrid nature of the hull-propeller-engine matching problem, PPO—being compatible with both discrete and continuous actions—is therefore a more appropriate choice for this problem.

Another challenge in hull-propeller-engine matching lies in the complexity of fuel consumption estimation. Ship resistance, the propeller-ship interaction, and engine performance are all highly nonlinear functions of design variables. While high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations can capture these phenomena in detail, they are computationally expensive and not the focus of this work. Therefore, surrogate models and semi-empirical approaches are sufficient for estimating fuel consumption within an optimization framework. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), for instance, have been successfully applied to resistance prediction: Yu and Wang [14] used a DNN to estimate resistance for different hull forms, achieving a test error as low as 0.942%. Semi-empirical formulas are also widely used; Birk [15] applied models originally developed by Andersen and Guldhammer [16] to predict wake fraction and thrust deduction fraction. Marques and Belchior [3] employed a polynomial regression approach to approximate engine fuel consumption performance, with a maximum fitting error below 2.7%.

Although the hull-propeller-engine system is complex involving numerous variables and constraints that result in a high-dimensional state and action space, a multi-agent system offers a promising approach to mitigate the curse of dimensionality by decomposing the problem into cooperative sub-tasks. However, existing studies often overlook the dynamic coupling between propulsion components and the ship’s geometry. To address these limitations, the main contribution of this paper can be summarized as follows: (1) We propose a novel energy consumption prediction model for RL environments. The hull, propeller and engine are modeled as interacting

agents, enabling information exchange and co-optimization to achieve feasible and efficient designs. (2) Inspired by the traditional design spiral, we formulate the matching process a sequential decision-making problem and develop a multi-agent framework to solve it. (3) The trained system demonstrated robustness to small variations in initial conditions and exhibits strong scalability, making it suitable for the hull-propeller-engine matching problem—a large-scale, high-dimensional design optimization problem.

This paper is organized as follows. Section Methods describes the cooperative multi-agent RL algorithms. Section Case study shows the application of the algorithm to the hull-propeller-engine matching problem. Section Conclusion concludes the advantages of the algorithm.

2. Methodology

The whole process defined in Section Methodology is shown in Figure 1.. It represents a standard workflow in RL methodologies, including an environment, a multi-agent system, and interaction between them.

RL is a type of machine learning that allows an agent or multi-agent system to learn by interacting with an environment, which is a structured space, like a simulator [17]. In this paper, the environment is a simulator that can simulate the fuel consumption of a ship, as shown in Figure 1.. A multi-agent system receives reward signal $R_{e,t}$ from the environment for each action they take, and the goal is to learn a policy π^θ that maximizes the cumulative reward over time, defined as follows:

$$\pi^\theta = \arg \max_{\pi} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} R_{e,t} \quad (1)$$

In this paper, for scalability and modularity, the cooperative multi-agent reinforcement learning algorithm is used to solve the hull-propeller-engine matching problem naturally. The hull, propeller and engine are each determined by at least one agent. Details are shown in the following sections.

Figure 1.: The whole process of the algorithm

2.1. Hull-propeller-engine Matching Problem in RL Framework

The Markov Decision Process is the mathematical framework for modeling reinforcement learning problems. The hull-propeller-engine matching problem can be considered as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), that is defined by the tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, p, r)$, where \mathcal{S} is the state space and the action space, \mathcal{A} is a discrete-continuous hybrid space, $p : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ is the transition function, and $r : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the reward function on each transition. In addition, what the tuple represents in the hull-propeller-engine matching problem is shown in the following section.

2.1.1. Action

An agent takes an action $A_t \in \mathcal{A}$ at the time step t , generated by its policy $\pi^\theta : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is usually a neural network with parameters θ , as shown in Figure 1.. There are four agents and their actions are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}_{1,t} &= (L_t, B_t) \\ \mathbf{A}_{2,t} &= (D_t, P_{\text{pi},t}, P_{\text{pl},t}) \\ \mathbf{A}_{3,t} &= (b_t) \\ \mathbf{A}_{4,t} &= (E_t) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $L_t \in [L_{\min}, L_{\max}]$ is the length of the hull at the time step t , $B_t \in [B_{\min}, B_{\max}]$ is the breadth of the hull, $D_t \in [D_{\min}, D_{\max}]$ is the diameter of the propeller, $P_{\text{pi},t} \in [P_{\text{pi},\min}, P_{\text{pi},\max}]$ is the pitch ratio of the propeller, $P_{\text{pl},t} \in [P_{\text{pl},\min}, P_{\text{pl},\max}]$ is the expanded area ratio (EAR) of the propeller, $b_t \in \mathcal{B}$ is the blade number of the propeller, and $E_t \in \mathcal{E}$ is the engine number. Specially, the propeller is determined by $\mathbf{A}_{2,t}$ and $\mathbf{A}_{3,t}$ because the blade number is discrete and others are continuous. E_t indicates the number of the engine in the database, which is discrete.

2.1.2. State

A state $S_t \in \mathcal{S}$ at the time step t can describe the current situation of the environment. For real world problems, the state of the environment is usually unknown by agents and $O_t \in \mathcal{O}$ is the observation of the environment received by agents. But in this paper, the environment is simulated, so the state is known. And it can be defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}_t = (L_t, B_t, D_t, P_{\text{pi},t}, P_{\text{pl},t}, b_t, E_t, R_t, \eta_t, g_t) \tag{3}$$

where R_t is the resistance of the hull at the time step t , η_t is the propeller efficiency, and g_t is the fuel consumption per hour. Agents receive two kinds of information from environment: One is the actual values of variables changed by their actions and another are some important computation results.

2.1.3. Transition Function

In the most general case, the transition function p is the density function of the probability distribution of the next state \mathbf{S}_{t+1} given the current state \mathbf{S}_t and the action $\mathbf{A}_{t,i}$. But the transition function is deterministic due to known environment in this paper. The next state \mathbf{S}_{t+1} can be computed by \mathbf{S}_t and $\mathbf{A}_{t,i}$ in environment, that shows the Markov property of the problem. Details on environment are given in the following section.

2.1.4. Reward Function

The reward R_e of hull-propeller-engine matching problem is the reduction in fuel consumption naturally, which is defined as follows:

$$R_{e,t} = -(g_t - g_{t-1}) - \mathbf{w} \mathbf{f}_{\text{penalty},t}^T \tag{4}$$

where $R_{e,t}$ is the reward of the environment at the time step t , $\mathbf{f}_{\text{penalty},t}$ is the penalty term associated with actions that exceed the limit, and \mathbf{w} is the weight of penalty. With fixed design

speed v_0 and fixed shipping route, the journey time is fixed and g_{ini} denotes the fuel consumption per unit time.

2.2. Environment of RL

In RL, the environment is still an important part, though some RL algorithms are model-free. The environment is a specific hull-propeller-engine model, which receives actions from agents, to compute fuel consumption. The model uses some techniques to reduce complexity of the problem and time-consumption of the simulation using some techniques. And the model is divided into three components: hull, propeller and engine naturally.

The hull part is a prediction model of the ship resistance R , which is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R &= R(L, B, v_0, d_{f0}, d_{a0}) \\ \Delta(L, B)_{\min} &\leq \Delta(L, B) \leq \Delta(L, B)_{\max} \\ C_b(L, B)_{\min} &\leq C_b(L, B) \leq C_b(L, B)_{\max} \\ \frac{L}{B}_{\min} &\leq \frac{L}{B} \leq \frac{L}{B}_{\max} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where length $L \in [L_{\min}, L_{\max}]$, breadth $B \in [B_{\min}, B_{\max}]$, displacement $\Delta(L, B)$, block coefficient $C_b(L, B)$, and ratio $\frac{L}{B}$ are bound to ensure the validity of the prediction model. The penalty based on displacement, block coefficient, and ratio is implemented to regulate the hull agent's actions in the reward function as mentioned above.

The specific form of the function $R(L, B, v_0, d_{f0}, d_{a0})$ where v_0 is the fixed design speed and, d_{f0} and d_{a0} are the fixed design fore and aft draft, will be complex, such as a CFD model or a Computational Potential Flow Model, if the model is high-fidelity.

But a surrogate model can be used to approximate these models with lower computational cost. Parametric modeling of the hull was conducted in CAESES [18], and SHIPFLOW [19] was used to compute the resistance and evaluate the resistance of the hull, enabling the construction of a reference database for resistance. A Radial Basis Function (RBF) model predicted the resistance based on computational data and a PR model predicted the displacement and wetted surface area. A hull agent determines length and breadth of the hull by policy and ship resistance is computed by the hull part.

The propeller part computes delivery power P_d according to ship resistance R . Wake fraction w_f and thrust deduction fraction t_f can reflect the interaction between the propeller and the hull, which are obtained by the method from Andersen and Guldhammer [16]. K_T and K_Q are determined by the propeller characteristics from propeller design diagrams, which are the Wageningen B-screw series in this paper. They can be computed by the advance factor J and the propeller design parameters P_{pi} , P_{pl} , and b :

$$\begin{aligned} K_T &= K_T(J, P_{pi}, P_{pl}, b) \\ K_Q &= K_Q(J, P_{pi}, P_{pl}, b) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Propeller design diagrams were constructed based on experimental data and can be used to design a propeller from the same series quickly. Therefore, agents generate a propeller by providing diameter, pitch ratio, EAR, and blade number and delivery power is obtained by propeller part.

An engine agent select an engine from engine database by policy. Then fuel consumption per hour g is computed by the SFC (Specific Fuel Consumption, g/kw · h) curve of the selected engine, which is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_e &= \frac{P_d}{\eta_t} \\ g &= \text{SFC}(P_e) \times P_e / 1000 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where P_e is the effective power of the engine, η_t is total efficiency from the engine to the propeller, and $\text{SFC}(P_e)$ indicates the relationship between the effective power and SFC. In the product brochure of the engine, some power-SFC data is given and can be used in polynomial fitting, which is less time-consuming.

2.3. Cooperative Multi-Agent System

PPO with Multi-Agent system (MAPPO) has been successfully developed in RL [20]. Therefore, MAPPO is used to train the cooperative multi-agent system. PPO is a policy gradient method that updates the policy by maximizing the probability ratio of the new policy $\pi^{\theta_{\text{new}}}$ and the old policy $\pi^{\theta_{\text{old}}}$. The objective function is defined as follows [12]:

$$\underset{\theta}{\text{maximize}} \quad \mathbb{E}_t \left[\frac{\pi_i^{\theta_{\text{new}}}(\mathbf{A}_{t,i}|\mathbf{S}_t)}{\pi_i^{\theta_{\text{old}}}(\mathbf{A}_{t,i}|\mathbf{S}_t)} \hat{A}_t \right] \quad (8)$$

where $\pi_i^{\theta_{\text{new}}}$ is the new policy of the agent i , $\pi_i^{\theta_{\text{old}}}$ is the old policy of the agent i , and \hat{A}_t is the advantage function that indicates the difference between the expected return of the new policy and the expected return at the state \mathbf{S}_t .

To overcome the problem of the non-stationary training, some techniques are used in PPO. An adaptive penalty on KL divergence and clipping method is used to constraint the difference between the new policy and the old policy [21][12] to prevent excessive policy updates.

And MAPPO is an extension of PPO for multi-agent systems. Compared with single-agent systems, multi-agent systems have more complex sequences of agent actions and interactions between agents. Based on the assumption that the hull-propeller-engine problem can be considered as a sequential decision problem, the sequence of agents action is one focus of this paper. As shown in Figure 2., there are three kinds of sequence of agents action: (1) All agents take actions at the same time and update the state. (2) Agents take actions and updates the state in the sequence of ship, propeller, and engine. (3) Agents take actions and updates the state in a random sequence.

Figure 2.: Sequence of agents action

3. Case study

3.1. Pre-training Work

A vessel is the target “environment” in the case study. The cooperative multi-agent system is trained to determine its optimal hull-propeller-engine configuration with the objective of minimizing fuel consumption. Basic information of the vessel and some constraints of model are shown in Table 1. and the parametric modeling of the hull is shown in Figure 3..

In the environment, the resistance prediction by the RBF model resulted in an R^2 of 0.990, and the displacement and wetted surface area prediction by the PR model resulted in an R^2 of 0.997. And the engine database includes the data of five diesels, which are shown in Table 2..

Before training, the MAPPO algorithm requires pre-defining the total number of iterations and the time steps per iteration. The multi-agent system explores and exploit the environment within time steps and updates the policy after each iteration.

Table 1.: Basic information of the vessel and some constraints of model

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Initial value of length	L_{ini}	181.7 m
Initial value of breadth	B_{ini}	26.5 m
Initial value of displacement	Δ_{ini}	18596.6 t
Initial value of block coefficient	$C_{b,ini}$	0.59
Design speed	v_0	20 knots
Design fore draft	d_{f0}	6.5 m
Design aft draft	d_{a0}	6.5 m
Initial of diameter	D_{ini}	4.80 m
Initial of pitch ratio	$P_{pi,ini}$	1.1739
Initial of EAR	$P_{pl,ini}$	0.6795
Initial of blade number	b_{ini}	4
Initial of engine number	E_{ini}	2
Number of propeller		2
Number of engine		2
Minimum of displacement	Δ_{min}	$0.99\Delta_{ini}$
Maximum of displacement	Δ_{max}	$1.01\Delta_{ini}$
Minimum of length-to-breadth ratio	$\frac{L}{B}_{min}$	$0.99\frac{L_{ini}}{B_{ini}}$
Maximum of length-to-breadth ratio	$\frac{L}{B}_{max}$	$1.01\frac{L_{ini}}{B_{ini}}$
Minimum of block coefficient	$C_{b,min}$	$0.99C_{b,ini}$
Maximum of block coefficient	$C_{b,max}$	$1.01C_{b,ini}$

Figure 3.: Parametric modeling of the hull

Table 2.: Engine database

Engine	Symbol	Power	N	SFC under full load
Engine 1	E_1	10800 kW	600 r/min	179.0 g/kW · h
Engine 2	E_2	10800 kW	500 r/min	189.9 g/kW · h
Engine 3	E_3	10800 kW	750 r/min	181.0 g/kW · h
Engine 4	E_4	10800 kW	514 r/min	182.0 g/kW · h
Engine 5	E_5	11700 kW	514 r/min	189.0 g/kW · h (10800kW)

3.2. Performance of MAPPO

The performance of MAPPO in the sequence (2) was evaluated relative to the initial configuration. Compared to the initial configuration, the length was increased by 1.0 m, while the breadth was decreased by 0.1 m. As a result, the length-to-breadth ratio decreased, while the block coefficient and displacement remained changed negligibly, indicating that the overall hull volume and shape remained largely consistent. The improvement in energy efficiency could be attributed to the optimized propeller configuration and engine selection, especially the latter, which achieved a notable decrease in SFC.

The Figure 4. shows the average fuel consumptions of 5 hull-propeller-engine configurations determined by some multi-agent systems trained under different iterations at the 2000th time step. The red dashed line represents the fuel consumption of the initial configuration. From the Figure 4., when the number of training iterations for agents is low, actions exceeding the soft constraints imposed by the penalty term may lead to numerically unreasonable fuel consumption values. And with the increase of the number of training iterations, fuel consumption converge to reasonable values and gradually stability. Perhaps the optimal configuration can be derived from other training time steps instead of 2000th to achieve lower fuel consumption. However, regardless of the lower fuel consumption, it is essential to validate the reasonability of the result. Moreover, the fuel consumption (1769 kg/h) of the configuration, shown in table 3., determined by the multi-agent system trained over 1000 iterations is reduced by 5% compared with the initial configuration (1864 kg/h). For the computational cost, training time is proportionate to the number of iterations. Using a workstation equipped with a 64-core Intel Xeon Gold 5218 CPU and one NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti GPU, 1000 iterations take approximately 45 minutes. However, based on the convergence trend of the fuel consumption, the model stabilizes well before reaching the full iteration count. This indicates that satisfactory performance can be achieved with fewer iterations, suggesting the potential for further reduction in training time improved computational efficiency.

Table 3.: Optimal configuration and fuel consumption compared with the initial configuration

Parameter	Initial configuration value	Optimal configuration value
Length	181.7 m	182.7 m
Breadth	26.5 m	26.4 m
Displacement	18596.6 t	18704.7 t
Block coefficient	0.59	0.59
Diameter	4.80 m	4.66 m
Pitch ratio	1.1739	1.1387
EAR	0.6795	0.6848
Number of blades	4	4
Number of engines	2	3
Fuel consumption	1864 kg/h	1769 kg/h

Figure 5. shows the action and fuel consumption trajectory over 2000 time steps from one iteration of the multi-agent system trained over 1000 iterations, which was selected as a representative example in the next section unless otherwise specified. As shown, actions are normalized to their respective ranges, and dashed lines represents their initial values. The adjustments to hull length and breadth are relatively small, with length remaining slightly above and breadth slightly below their initial values. Notably, the hull has already undergone preliminary optimized using traditional optimization methods. However, slight increase in length and reduction in breadth contribute to improved performance slightly. The multi-agent system consistently drives the diameter and pitch ratio toward their lower bounds, indicating a preference for smaller propeller configuration. Among the continuous actions, EAR exhibits the strongest influence on fuel consumption. For discrete actions, the system stabilizes at 4 blades and No.3 engine, suggesting these configurations are optimal under the given constraints.

Figure 4.: Fuel consumption of different iterations and training time

Figure 5.: Action and fuel consumption trajectory of one iteration

3.3. Performance in Different Environments

In the training environment, design speed, design aft draft, and design fore draft are fixed. To evaluate the robustness of the multi-agent system trained using MAPPO, these parameters are deliberately changed. This ability to generalize across varying conditions highlights a fundamental distinction between RL and traditional optimization algorithms. Trained multi-agent system can adapt to modified environments and efficiently converge to a new optimal configuration. In contrast, the optimal given by traditional optimization algorithms is typically a fixed point, highly sensitive to the changes in environment parameters. As such, re-optimization from scratch is often required when conditions change. The parameter settings used in these robustness tests are shown in Table 4.

Table 4.: Parameters of different environments

Environment	Speed	Aft Draft	Fore Draft	Fuel Consumption
Initial	20 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	1864 kg/h
1	24 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	3096 kg/h
2	23 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	2718 kg/h
3	22 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	2391 kg/h
4	21 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	2104 kg/h
5	19 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	1613 kg/h
6	18 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	1401 kg/h
7	17 knots	6.5 m	6.5 m	1207 kg/h

To evaluate robustness, the multi-agent system trained in the baseline environment, 7 variant environments were constructed by systematically varying the design speed, range from 17.0 to 24.0 knots in 1.0-knot increments. In each case, the system’s fuel consumption was measured over a short horizon of 5 time steps, with results compared against the baseline performance of the initial configuration. The results are shown in Figure 6.. As shown, the trained multi-agent system in the initial environment (20.0 knots) achieves lower fuel consumption than the initial configuration in all environments, demonstrating effective generalization. However, performance gradually degrades as the environment deviation from the training condition increases, indicating a limit to its robustness under large changes. Notably the system’s performance after only 5 time steps is nearly indistinguishable from its performance after 2000 time steps. This suggesting that the agents can rapidly adapt to new but similar environments, highlighting their strong generalization capability and suitability for dynamic design scenarios.

3.4. Influence of the Sequence of Agents Action

Following the methodology used for sequence (2), multi-agent systems in the sequence (1) and (3) were trained for 1000 iterations, with each iteration comprising 10000 time steps. The fuel consumption trajectories of all three systems—evaluated over 2000 time steps in the initial environment—are shown in Figure 7.. The results demonstrate that the order in which agents take actions significantly influences overall system performance. Specifically, the system with the sequence (2) achieves the lowest fuel consumption, followed by the sequence (1), while sequence (3) yields the highest fuel consumption among the three. The performance gap can be attributed to the impact of action sequencing on inter-agent information flow and coordination. Sequence (2), which aligns with the physical energy flow in the ship system, facilitates more effective communication and decision-making among agents, In contrast, sequence (3)—a randomly ordered sequence—disrupts this natural dependency structure, leading to suboptimal coordination and slower convergence. These findings suggest that designing action sequences based on physical causality or system dynamics enhances learning efficiency and final policy quality in multi-agent reinforcement learning for ship design optimization.

Figure 6.: Fuel consumption of different environments

Figure 7.: Fuel consumption of different sequences

4. Conclusion and Future Work

RL algorithms have been successfully applied to the hull-propeller-engine matching problem. The results showed that the proposed approach can achieve 5% reduction in the fuel consumption compared to the initial design. Although the time of training was relatively long, the trained system could be used to quickly generate a new design for different design requirements, such as different ship speeds. Assigning agent-specific reward functions within a multi-agent framework facilitated the development of agents with distinct functional capabilities. For example, displacement and block coefficient were considered as a penalty function for the hull agent. The scalability and modularity of RL algorithms in the hull-propeller-engine matching problem were demonstrated. The results of the sequence of agents action showed that the agent frameworks in multi-agent system had a significant impact on the performance of the system.

Future work will focus on the reduction of the training time and the extension of the application to more general design problems. Expert knowledge will be integrated into the training process and a more reasonable agent framework will be developed to enhance the performance of the multi-agent system.

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